

An NMR-based metabolomics strategy for adulteration detection of natural resins: Application to Chios mastic gum

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ABSTRACT

Chios mastic gum (CMG), the resin from *Pistacia lentiscus* L. var. *Chia*, is a valuable natural product with a long history of therapeutic use and significant economic impact. However, its authenticity is increasingly challenged by adulteration with chemically similar resins, particularly *Pistacia atlantica*. This study presents a robust ¹H NMR-based metabolomics approach combined with principal component analysis (PCA) to authenticate CMG and distinguish it from other resins. A total of 131 resin samples—including 71 authentic CMG samples from four Chios subregions—were analyzed. A distinct metabolic signature for CMG was revealed, primarily characterized by high levels of masticadienonic acid (MNA), isomasticadienonic acid (IMNA), oleanonic aldehyde, and *cis*-1,4-poly- β -myrcene. The resulting chemometric model effectively differentiated CMG from adulterants, including Iranian mastic gum (IMG) and aged CMG, and identified mislabeled commercial samples. Two authentication indices (MA Index-1 and MA Index-2) were developed based on key metabolite concentrations and their ratios, providing a quantifiable, reproducible framework for CMG quality control. This method enables rapid, non-destructive authentication without extensive sample preparation or reference standards, offering a valuable tool for safeguarding the integrity of CMG in commercial and regulatory settings.

1. Introduction

Resins are plant-derived secretions consisting of volatile and non-volatile secondary metabolites, mainly terpenes and phenolic compounds, and are often produced by plants in response to stress or as means of defense [1].

A resin with long history and documented health promoting properties is Chios mastic gum (CMG), the aromatic resin obtained from the mastic tree *Pistacia lentiscus* L. var. *Chia* (Anacardiaceae), cultivated in the Greek island of Chios, through trunk incisions. It is well known for its wide array of applications in the pharmaceuticals, foods and cosmetics industries [2]. Moreover, in 1997 it was attributed the “Protected Designation of Origin (PDO)” label by the European Union, and its way of cultivation was recognized as an Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity by UNESCO in 2014 [3,4]. A broad range of biological properties have been attributed to CMG over the years, from antioxidant and anti-inflammatory to chemopreventive and cardioprotective [2]. In

2016, a significant milestone was reached, as the European Medicines Agency (EMA) published a monograph recognizing the resin of *Pistacia lentiscus* as a traditional herbal medicinal product [5]. The monograph outlines two primary indications: the management of mild dyspeptic disorders and the treatment of skin inflammations, including the promotion of healing in minor wounds. Because CMG is PDO-restricted to southern Chios and commands a premium price in food, cosmetic and medicinal markets, supply chains often involve repackaging outside the producer cooperative’s direct oversight, factors that heighten both the incentive and the opportunity for fraud.

Due to its distinctive qualities and lengthy history, CMG constitutes a highly prized commercial product and a valuable resource for the island of Chios with more than 250 tons of exports per year [2,6], making it also a target for adulteration. Dioscoride was the first to report the adulteration of CMG with pine resin or frankincense as one of the first known references of a natural product’s adulteration [7]. According to the Hellenic Ministry of Rural Development and Food, CMG is

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susceptible to adulteration, which may occur independently or in conjunction with counterfeit packaging. In most cases, such fraudulent products contain Iranian mastic (*Pistacia atlantica*) or other lower quality resins, but are mislabeled with the branding of the Chios Mastic Growers Association (CMGA). These practices have been predominantly reported in countries such as Syria, Egypt, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates [8]. In practical terms, three fraud modes cause the most concern: (i) substitution with chemically similar resins (particularly *P. atlantica*), (ii) blending with cheaper materials/resins (e.g., pine, *Boswellia*, dammar), and (iii) mislabeling/counterfeit packaging that mimics CMGA branding.

Regarding its chemical composition, CMG is a highly complex natural resin with the predominant chemical group being triterpenes, which account for about 65–70 % of the total resin weight. In addition, CMG contains a variety of volatile compounds found in its essential oil and mastic water—two byproducts obtained through the distillation of the gum. Furthermore, a small proportion (~5 %) of CMG consists of compounds from diverse chemical classes. These constituents are embedded within the resin matrix, which is structured primarily by a polymer, *cis*-1,4-poly- β -myrcene, that makes up approximately 20–30 % of the gum's dry weight [6,9,10]. The presence of this polymer causing issues with sample handling and common analytical approaches employing chromatography, and the absence of commercially available standards enhances adulteration phenomena [2]. The European Pharmacopoeia monograph currently evaluates CMG's quality through essential oil content and its profile using thin-layer chromatography (TLC) [11]. Aside from the official method, several attempts have been made over the years, mainly focusing on mastic oil or certain target compounds. For instance, chiral GC-MS has been used for essential oil analysis and adulteration detection [12], while LC-HRMS/MS has only enabled detailed metabolite profiling through extensive sample preparation such as polymer removal [13,14]. Furthermore, two validated HPLC-UV methods targeting oleanonic acid have been proposed [15], although this compound lacks taxonomic specificity due to its wide occurrence in the plant kingdom. Recently, a high-performance thin-layer chromatography (HPTLC) method has been introduced as a more efficient alternative to the TLC and distillation-based criteria currently employed in the official monograph, but it is proposed as a means for profile characterization and aging evaluation rather than authenticity assessment [16]. Additionally, a promising HPLC-ELSD method was introduced by Svingou et al. [17] quantifying masticadienonic and isomasticadienonic acids (MNA and IMNA), CMG's major triterpenes, in samples containing mastic. Nevertheless, this method is specific to those compounds and does not account for the entire metabolite profile of CMG, so adulterants that also contain these acids (e.g., *P. atlantica*) could still pass a single-analyte test.

To bridge this gap, plant metabolomics provides a more complete and insightful way to approach quality assessment [18]. In the context of plant metabolomics, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy stands out as a robust analytical tool for profiling complex natural matrices. It enables the simultaneous detection of a wide range of metabolites without the need for extensive sample preparation or compound-specific standards [19,20]. Additionally, NMR, both solution and solid-state, due to its numerous advantages, has found a plethora of applications in biomedical and pharmaceutical analysis, as well as the analysis of naturally occurring materials [21,22]. This makes NMR particularly valuable for quality control in natural products, where chemical complexity and variability are high. Accordingly, our goal was to develop a ^1H -NMR profiling approach that captures the characteristic CMG signature (triterpenes, aldehydes, and polymer), pair it with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to visualize class separation, and formalize two simple numerical screens—MA Index-1 (sum of MNA/IMNA + aldehydes) and MA Index-2 (their ratio)—that translate the metabolomic fingerprint into operational quality control criteria. By combining NMR data with PCA, the aim was to construct a robust statistical model that can reliably distinguish genuine mastic gum from the

island of Chios from other adulterated products and resins. This approach supports the development of an efficient quality control framework that safeguards consumer trust and preserves the identity of this historically significant natural product.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample collection

A total of 131 resin samples were collected for this study. Specifically, 71 samples were authentic CMG provided by the CMGA from 4 different regions/fields of the southern part of Chios Island and 60 samples were either commercially available or collected from other known plants. Details for each sample can be found in Table S1. For commercial samples in particular, a dedicated column states the declaration found on the label. The 4 Aged CMG samples – 2, 10, ~50 years and fossilized – were provided by CMGA. They were stored under ambient and dark conditions. Aging conclusions are therefore comparisons to naturally aged material rather than a controlled study. All samples were stored safely in sealed packages under dark conditions and at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ until analysis as some samples were hygroscopic.

2.2. NMR analysis

2.2.1. Sample preparation

Firstly, each sample was finely ground with a mortar and pestle. Then, 15 mg (± 0.1) of powder from each sample were accurately weighed. Samples were dissolved in 700 μL of deuterated chloroform-*d* (99.8 % D, Merck SA, Athens, Greece) containing 0.02 % v/v hexamethyldisiloxane (HMDSO NMR grade, Sigma-Aldrich Corporation, St. Louis, MO, USA) as an internal standard and a line-shape indicator. 650 μL of each sample were transferred into a 5 mm NMR tube (D600) with a PTFE cap (Deutero GmbH, Kastellaun, Germany). Due to its volatility, chloroform-*d* was handled using a positive-displacement pipette (MICROMAN®, Gilson Inc., Middleton, WI, USA).

2.2.2. Experimental parameters

^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE III 600 MHz spectrometer equipped with a BBI probe with z-gradients using the noesygp1d pulse sequence and the following conditions: number of scans (ns), 128; $\pi/2$ pulse, $\sim 8\text{ }\mu\text{s}$; TD, 64k data points; acquisition time, 3.03 sec; relaxation delay (d1), 2.00 sec; spectral width, 10822.51 Hz; transmitter frequency offset (O1), 3600.66 and receiver gain (rg), 64. Temperature was kept stable at 305 K with the help of a Bruker Cooling Unit (BCU), while the ICON software (Bruker AG, Faellanden, Switzerland) was used to control automated acquisition with the help of a Bruker Automated Control System with 60 positions (B-ACS 60). The spectra were obtained by FT of the FID by applying an exponential function with a line broadening factor (lb) of 0.3 Hz and zero-filling (size = 128k). Resulting spectra were automatically phase- and baseline-corrected in the Bruker TopSpin software (4.4.1). Chemical shifts were reported with respect to the IS's signal set at 0.0 ppm. Additionally, HSQC-DEPT and JRES spectra were acquired for certain samples to aid in the identification process.

2.2.3. Data processing and statistical multivariate analysis

The raw data obtained from NMR were first imported into the MATLAB suite (R2024b) for processing. Using the icoshift tool [23] and a tailored selection of intervals optimized for the sample type, the spectra were aligned. Aligned spectra were binned for the selected spectral width from -0.5 – 14.0 ppm into 1451 equal-sized bins of 0.01 ppm each. After baseline noise and solvent peak removal, the bins were reduced to 1063. Data were then imported into SIMCA v. 17.0.2 (Sartorius AG, Göttingen, Germany), where they were subjected to multivariate analysis (MVA). Specifically, Principal Component Analysis (PCA), an unsupervised method, was used for the construction of the

statistical model, following the application of pareto scaling to the dataset. The optimum number of principal components used to construct every model was determined using the “autofit” tool provided by the software that employs defined cross-validation rules (7 cross-validation rounds and a maximum of 200 iterations). No outliers were detected in the PCA model containing only CMG samples using Hotelling’s T^2 . Outliers were not excluded in the second PCA model containing all samples due to the expected significant variability among them (most non-CMG samples would have been considered outliers). ANOVA was performed to assess the significant differences between the sample groups. Tukey’s HSD post-hoc tests were used for multiple comparisons of means ($p < 0.05$). Violin plots were employed to visualize the ANOVA data. Univariate analyses were carried out using GraphPad Prism 9.0.0 (GraphPad Software Inc., CA, USA). All computations for the MA Index-1 (sum of MNA/IMNA and aldehydes) and MA Index-2 (ratio) were performed in R (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, v 4.5.1, Vienna, Austria). Index ranges were calibrated on the authentic CMG cohort ($n = 71$; Table S4) using a symmetric guard-band policy ($\text{min}/\text{max} \pm k\text{-SD}$) and evaluated by leave-one-out cross-validation (Tables S5-S7). Bootstrap confidence intervals (10,000 resamples) were computed for the acceptance bounds, showing stability to sampling variation (Table S8). Tables were exported to docx with officer/flexible and to xlsx with openxlsx.

3. Results and discussion

With the escalating global demand for Chios mastic and its formal classification by EMA as a traditional herbal medicinal product, the imperative for stringent quality assurance protocols has grown substantially. One of the primary challenges threatening the integrity and commercial viability of CMG is the issue of adulteration—most notably, the substitution or mixing of the resin with Iranian mastic, a substance that is chemically distinct yet visually similar. This concern is further exacerbated by modern distribution practices, where bulk sales and repackaging frequently disconnect the product from the certification and traceability provided by the CMGA. To combat these risks and uphold the authenticity of Chios mastic in both domestic and international markets, this study exploits NMR spectroscopy as a reliable and non-destructive analytical method for quality control. By integrating multivariate statistical techniques, specifically PCA, with NMR spectral data, we aim to construct a robust chemometric model capable of discerning genuine CMG from adulterated or counterfeit products with high sensitivity and specificity. This approach not only enhances supply chain transparency but also fortifies regulatory compliance by providing scientifically validated tools for authentication. Ultimately, the adoption of such methodologies supports the long-term sustainability of the Chios mastic industry and reinforces consumer trust in certified natural products originating from the island of Chios.

3.1. Authentic Chios mastic gum characterization

The importance of authentic samples in metabolomics studies is pivotal in order to have a solid basis for an authentication statistical model [24]. To that end, 71 fresh CMG samples from different subregions from the southern part of Chios Island were kindly provided by the CMGA. The first step was to record the metabolic profile of all CMG samples and try to detect any variations based on the different geographical origin. The extracted data of the ^1H NMR profiles of the CMG samples were subjected to an unsupervised statistical approach, namely PCA, a widely adopted chemometric method, that streamlines data by identifying principal components that account for the greatest variance. Since PCA does not require predefined group classifications, it can uncover patterns and clusters based on shared characteristics across different samples. A total of 11 principal components were used for the construction of the PCA model with the first three accounting for more than 70 % of the total variance. As can be observed in the PCA scores

scatter plot (Fig. 1), no pattern could be discerned between the samples from the four different subregions. This could be an indication that the resin is a chemically stable matrix, unaffected by the harvesting region. While prior studies have focused on *P. lentiscus* seed oils from Tunisia and Morocco, highlighting the influence of geographic and pedoclimatic factors on phenolic composition [25,26], limited research exists on CMG resin differentiation within Chios. In a study by Paraschos et al. [12], no significant variation in essential oil quality among resins from different Chios localities was detected, corroborating our findings.

Furthermore, an extensive dereplication attempt was made to characterize as many compounds as possible in the ^1H NMR spectrum of authentic CMG (Fig. 2). Significant overlapping could be observed in the aliphatic region due to the methyl protons of triterpenoids, with alkenyl protons being easier to distinguish. Two-dimensional NMR spectra were acquired to increase identification confidence. Aside from existing literature, an in-house library of isolated compounds was used for identification. Most of the identified compounds belonged to the class of triterpenoids. Among them, the most abundant were MNA, IMNA and oleanonic aldehyde.

3.2. Resins’ authentication by NMR and chemometrics

Expanding the statistical model using NMR data to include various resins and commercial samples could provide a solution for assessing the quality and authenticity of plant resins, among them CMG, as it captures their complex chemical profiles with high reproducibility. In pursuit of that, 60 more resins or commercial samples were collected and analyzed using the same workflow. Details about the number and type of these samples can be found in Table S1. Different authentic resins and gums, i. e. *Pinus* sp., dammar, *Boswellia* sp., *Cupressus* sp., and other *Pistacia* sp., were included in order to build a statistical model that could differentiate between them and help in the authentication of CMG. Among the included samples were aged CMG to explore the aging effect on its chemical composition and examine whether the constructed statistical model could distinguish between fresh and aged CMG. Indicative ^1H NMR spectra from each category are presented in Fig. S1.

The PCA scores scatter plot (Fig. 3A) revealed: (i) a compact fresh CMG cluster; (ii) aged CMG displaced mainly along PC1, consistent with volatile loss and matrix changes upon storage; (iii) IMG situated nearer to aged CMG than to fresh CMG, reflecting partial overlap in triterpenoids but distinct monoterpene/aldehyde balance; (iv) clear separation of other taxa (pine, *Boswellia*, dammar, *Cupressus*); and (v) four commercial items plotting inside the CMG domain. The four commercial samples that fell within the CMG group were RS099, RS123, RS126 and RS127. By examining again their ^1H NMR spectra, these samples seemed to have the exact profile as all CMG samples, indicating that they are indeed authentic and confirming the predictive ability of the model. Another group formed involved aged CMG samples, separated from fresh CMG by the first principal component, suggesting changes in their chemical composition. One of the main issues with mastic resin during storage is that it loses its essential oils while simultaneously becoming harder, which leads to a lower-quality and less valuable product. According to earlier research, mastic gum can be thought of as a system made up of a resin and a solvent, and the main reason the product hardens is because of the latter’s evaporation [27]. Moreover, another study showed that during storage myrcene decreases and α -pinene increases in mastic samples, as a result their ratio can serve as an indicator of aging. Iranian mastic gum from *Pistacia atlantica*, one of the main adulterants of CMG, was also well-separated from fresh CMG samples. As evidenced by their proximity in the PCA scores scatter plot, Iranian mastic gum (IMG) exhibited a metabolite profile that partially overlaps with aged CMG. This spatial relationship suggests a degree of chemical similarity between IMG and aged CMG, likely arising from shared triterpenoid constituents such as MNA and IMNA. However, despite these overlaps, IMG is chemically distinct from fresh CMG, possibly displaying lower concentrations of key biomarkers and a greater abundance of

Fig. 1. PCA scores scatter plot based on the first two principal components showing the 71 authentic CMG samples colored based on different subregion from the island of Chios – $R2X(\text{cum}) = 0.972$, $Q2(\text{cum}) = 0.907$.

Fig. 2. Annotated representative 1D ^1H NMR spectrum of Chios mastic gum (CMG) (600 MHz, chloroform- d , reference with IS at 0 ppm). 1: masticadienonic acid (MNA); 2: isomasticadienonic acid (IMNA); 3: oleanonic acid; 4: oleanonic acid; 5: moronic acid; 6: *cis*-1,4-poly- β -myrcene; 7: 28-nor-oleanone; 8: oleanonic aldehyde; 9: oleanonic aldehyde; 10: masticadienonal; 11: isomasticadienonal; 12: masticadienolic acid; 13: isomasticadienolic acid; 14: betulonal; 15: lup-20(29)-en-3-one; 16: caryophyllene oxide. The spectral region from 9.6 to 2.3 ppm has been scaled 16 times to enhance visibility of minor peaks.

monoterpenes such as α -pinene and limonene which are not prominent in authentic CMG, as indicated by literature [28,29]. The convergence of IMG and aged CMG in the plot likely reflects the degradative changes occurring in CMG over time—primarily the loss of volatile components and reduction in certain triterpenoids—rather than true compositional equivalence. This observation highlights the importance of considering sample age and post-harvest changes in authentication studies and reinforces the need for robust chemical markers to distinguish genuine CMG from similar, but non-equivalent, resins like IMG.

To better understand which metabolites drive this separation, we examined the respective loadings plot of the PCA model to locate discriminant bins and then assigned them using 1D/2D NMR and reference spectra (Table S2). Those metabolites are the so-called biomarkers which can be measured and replicated, and their concentrations indicate differences and help with identification [30]. The loadings plot highlights four CMG-enriched discriminants—MNA, IMNA, oleanonic aldehyde, and *cis*-1,4-poly- β -myrcene—that map to diagnostic bins (Table S2; Figs S2, S3): MNA/IMNA show the olefinic H-24 at 5.99–6.03

Fig. 3. A. PCA scores scatter plot based on the first two principal components showing all analyzed samples colored based on botanical origin – R2X(cum) = 0.848, Q2(cum) = 0.546. B. Respective loadings scatter plot with statistically significant compounds annotated.

ppm (δ_C 147.1); oleanonic aldehyde gives a distinctive H-28 at 9.34 ppm (δ_C 207.4), and *cis*-1,4-poly- β -myrcene (the dominant matrix polymer of CMG) contributes broad 5.05 ppm signals (δ_C 124.5). These attributions were not based on PCA alone; they were confirmed by HSQC-DEPT cross-peaks and overlays with pure compounds (Fig. 4). As can be seen in Fig. 4, there is a complete overlap between the features positively correlating with CMG in the contribution plot and the peaks of the respective compounds. The chemical structures of these compounds are presented in Fig. 5. The importance in their contribution to the biological activity of the crude resin is mentioned in the assessment report of EMA, where the pure polymer, followed by the acidic fraction of CMG (mainly comprised by MNA/IMNA) are noted for their activity against *Helicobacter pylori* [31].

To further characterize the other natural resin and gum samples the ^1H NMR spectra obtained were also examined combined with HSQC-DEPT spectra in order to identify certain characteristic compounds in each one. IMG, pine resin, dammar gum, resins from *Boswellia* sp. and *Cupressus* sp. demonstrated clear compositional differences, confirming the utility of NMR spectroscopy in the chemical differentiation and authentication of plant-derived resins (Fig. S2-S6). The ^1H NMR spectrum of IMG (Fig. S2) shares some overlapping triterpenoids with CMG (e.g., MNA, IMNA), but exhibits higher α -pinene/limonene (\approx 5.12/4.75 ppm) and lower aldehydes (9.34 ppm) content, which explains its proximity to aged CMG in the PCA scores scatter plot [32,33]. The

remaining resin samples exhibit markedly different spectral profiles, reflecting their distinct botanical origins and chemical compositions. For instance, pine resin was found to be notably rich in monoterpenes α/β -pinene and abietane/pimarane diterpenes (e.g., abietic/isopimaric/dehydroabietic acids with diagnostic proton signals – Table S2), as verified by literature [34–36], indicating a terpenoid profile that is fundamentally different from that of CMG. On the other hand, dammar gum displayed a distinct set of dammarane-type triterpenes, including dammaradienone and dammarenic acid [37,38], which are typical constituents of dammar resins, along with oleanonic aldehyde. The spectrum of *Boswellia* resin is defined by the presence of 11-keto- β -boswellic acid a triterpenoid that is well-recognized as a chemotaxonomic marker for *Boswellia* species [39,40], again depleted in CMG-typical triterpenes and aldehyde. In contrast, *Cupressus* resin shows a predominance of α -pinene and sandaracopimaric acid, indicating a diterpenoid-rich composition characteristic of coniferous species [41–43]. Characteristic signals (^1H and ^{13}C) of the compounds identified from each sample are listed in Table S2. These spectral distinctions further validate the capacity of ^1H NMR spectroscopy to discriminate between closely related natural products based on their unique metabolite signatures.

Fig. 4. A. Contribution plot for the CMG group compared to the model average (extracted from the PCA model). The linear combinations of the first and second principal components' p loadings were used as weights (p1, p2); B. ¹H NMR spectrum of oleanonic aldehyde; C. ¹H NMR spectrum of IMNA; D. ¹H NMR spectrum of MNA; E. ¹H NMR spectrum of *cis*-1,4-poly-β-myrcene.

3.3. Establishment of an authentication index for Chios mastic gum

The final step of this study was to try to establish an index using the statistically significant compounds indicated from the PCA model. At first, using violin plots, we examined the relative concentrations of MNA/IMNA and oleanonic aldehyde in five sample categories to assess the chemical uniqueness of CMG and how it differs from other resinous materials. For MNA/IMNA the sum of NMR bins at 5.99–6.03 ppm was

used, as there was no significant overlapping observed in that region of the spectrum. The compounds masticadienolic and isomasticadienolic acid with their olefinic H-24 resonating at that region, are in significantly lower concentrations and do not marginally affect the area of the integrated peak. For oleanonic aldehyde, the aldehydic proton resonating at 9.34 ppm (NMR bin 9.34 ppm) was selected. In this case, overlapping was observed at this signal with the compounds betulonal and oleanolic aldehyde, as detected in the HSQC-DEPT spectrum. These

Fig. 5. Chemical structures of key biomarkers for CMG's differentiation, namely MNA, IMNA, oleanonic aldehyde and *cis*-1,4-poly-β-myrcene.

compounds were in markedly lower abundance than oleanonic aldehyde in CMG samples, as verified by the ratio of other non-overlapping peaks (5.5–4.5 ppm). However, the decision was made to use their sum to construct the violin plots.

Looking at the first violin plot (Fig. 6A), CMG samples seemed to

exhibit the highest and most consistent concentrations, indicated by the tight distribution of points clustered around a high median value. This suggests a strong presence of these biomarkers in CMG, reinforcing their diagnostic utility. Aged CMG shows a moderate reduction in MNA/IMNA levels, likely due to degradation over time, but still retains

Fig. 6. Violin plots with samples distributed in five categories; CMG, aged CMG, IMG, commercial samples and other resins; considering A. the sum of MNA and IMNA (NMR bins 5.99–6.03 ppm), B. the sum of oleanonic aldehyde, betulonal and oleanonic aldehyde (NMR bin 9.34 ppm). Statistically significant levels in favor of CMG were observed in both plots. Results of Tukey's HSD post-hoc tests for multiple comparisons of means are presented in Table S3.

distinguishable levels above most other categories. IMG and commercial samples display more variability and generally lower concentrations, indicating that these may not be chemically identical to authentic CMG or may contain only partial similarities. Finally, the “Other resins” category shows the lowest and most dispersed values, reinforcing its chemical dissimilarity to CMG. The second violin plot (Fig. 6B) illustrates the relative abundance of oleanonic aldehyde, betulonal and oleanolic aldehyde. Hereby, a similar trend is observed. CMG again stands out with the highest aldehyde levels, further validating its unique chemical profile. Aged CMG and IMG show significantly reduced aldehyde content, suggesting either age-related degradation or botanical differences. Interestingly, some commercial samples show moderate levels of aldehyde, hinting at possible adulteration or partial inclusion of CMG-like material. The “Other” samples cluster near the baseline, showing negligible aldehyde content and thus affirming their unrelated origin. Those results, align with previous studies, where Sharifi et al. [44] compared CMG to subspecies of *Pistacia atlantica* and found that key compounds of their acidic fractions such as MNA and IMNA were detected in higher amounts in CMG.

The final goal of this study was to translate these results into something measurable, and tangible as would be for instance a quality index. Based on our observations of the violin plots, the first condition should be to have sufficiently high levels of both the triterpenic acids MNA/IMNA and the three aldehydes (oleanonic aldehyde, betulonal and oleanolic aldehyde). If that criterion was met, the second condition could be a certain ratio between these triterpenic acids and aldehydes. To that end, we proposed for the first condition the Mastic Authentication Index 1 or MA Index-1 and for the second MA Index-2, respectively, where:

$$\text{MA Index - 1} = \text{Area}_{\text{MNA/IMNA}} + \text{Area}_{\text{aldehydes}}$$

$$\text{MA Index - 2} = \frac{\text{Area}_{\text{MNA/IMNA}}}{\text{Area}_{\text{aldehydes}}}$$

The values for all samples were calculated based on these equations (Table S4). Thresholds for each index were derived from the authentic CMG distribution with small guard bands (Tables S5, S6). For MA Index-1, the acceptable range was determined between $6.26\text{E}+06$ – $1.13\text{E}+07$, and, for MA Index-2, between 2.28 and 6.34 (Table S6). Based on these ranges, commercial samples and other resins were assessed as to whether they met one, both, or none of the set criteria. Among the samples examined, only four were found to meet both, commercial samples RS099, RS123, RS126 and RS127 (Table S9). These samples were the exact same ones that fell within the CMG group in the constructed PCA model, indicating once again the prediction ability of the model for the authenticity assessment of CMG. Moreover, the agreement between the output of the model and the indices further establishes the proposed indices with their respective acceptable ranges as an efficient method for the quality control of CMG. This is the first time, to our knowledge, that a quick ^1H NMR-based method is proposed for the streamlined and rapid quality control of CMG. The addition of more samples in the future could expand the model’s applicability towards the quality control of other resins or gum products.

4. Conclusion

The increasing global demand for CMG, coupled with its economic and cultural significance, highlights the urgent need for effective quality control strategies that ensure product authenticity and guard against adulteration. In this study, we developed a ^1H NMR-based metabolomics workflow integrated with multivariate statistical analysis to provide a reliable, reproducible, and non-destructive method for the authentication of CMG. Using 131 resin samples—including authentic CMG from multiple subregions of Chios, aged CMG, commercial products, and resins from other botanical sources—we demonstrated the effectiveness of PCA in resolving complex metabolite profiles and in clearly separating genuine CMG from other sample types. Through dereplication efforts

and comparative spectral analysis, several key biomarkers were identified—most notably masticadienonic acid (MNA), isomasticadienonic acid (IMNA), oleanonic aldehyde, and *cis*-1,4-poly- β -myrcene—as characteristic of authentic CMG. Their presence and concentration levels proved instrumental in differentiating CMG from common adulterants such as Iranian mastic (*P. atlantica*) and from aged or degraded samples. To further strengthen the model’s practical utility, two quantitative indices were introduced—MA Index-1 and MA Index-2—based on the abundance and ratio of these diagnostic compounds. These indices successfully classified CMG samples and detected authentic commercial products with high sensitivity and specificity, in agreement with the PCA model predictions. This dual approach not only enhances the robustness of CMG authentication, but also provides an accessible and scalable tool for routine quality assessment in regulatory and industrial settings. Overall, this study represents the first comprehensive application of NMR metabolomics and chemometrics for the systematic authentication of CMG. The proposed methodology has the potential to become a cornerstone in quality control practices for mastic gum and similar resinous products, while future expansion of the model may extend its applicability to other complex natural matrices.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Maria Halabalaki: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Eleftherios Kalpoutzakis:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Ilias Smyrnioudis:** Resources, Methodology. **Vasiliki K. Pachi:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Eleni Akrivousi:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Stavros Beteinakis:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jpba.2025.117285](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2025.117285).

Data Availability

The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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